

AN EXAMINATION OF SOCIAL WORKERS' PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCES DURING THE PANDEMIC FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF SOCIAL WORK EDUCATION

Keywords

Social work,

COVID-19,

Pandemic,

Crisis management,

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the professional experiences of social workers in Turkey during the COVID-19 pandemic from the perspective of social work education and to evaluate the adequacy of the current curriculum in the context of crisis management. The study was conducted using the phenomenological design, a qualitative research method, and employed a semi-structured interview technique for data collection. The study group consisted of a total of 12 social workers who were actively working during the pandemic and had graduated from universities with similar curricula. The data obtained were analyzed using a descriptive analysis method. The research findings reveal that significant changes occurred in the professional roles of social workers during the pandemic. In particular, it was determined that psychosocial support and empowerment-based practices took a backseat, while social assistance and logistical activities came to the forefront. In addition, it was observed that the training process falls short in terms of crisis management, rapid decision-making, psychosocial intervention, and practice-based skills. Furthermore, it was found that professionals lack supervision and institutional support mechanisms, and that this situation increases the risk of professional burnout. Based on these findings, it was concluded that social work education programs should incorporate courses on crisis management and disaster response into the curriculum, increase practical training, strengthen psychosocial support skills, and develop supervision systems. The study offers significant contributions toward making social work education more prepared and resilient in the face of future crises.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has gone down in history as a major crisis that has transformed the lifestyles of individuals and societies on a global scale.¹ In addition to the pandemic's direct health impacts, it is noted to have significant consequences such as the deepening of social inequalities, the increase in socio-economic disparities, and the widespread emergence of mental health issues.²⁻

³ Social workers have played critical roles by providing support to the most vulnerable segments of society during the pandemic.⁴⁻⁶ With the pandemic, issues such as changes in roles within the social work field, transformations in how professionals work, and the restructuring of service delivery methods have come to the forefront.⁷⁻⁸

With the onset of the pandemic, the primary responsibilities of social workers have included crisis management, enhancing community resilience, providing psychosocial support, and continuing services—particularly for vulnerable groups.⁹⁻¹⁰ However, pandemic conditions—including the need to reduce physical contact and the imposition of social isolation—have made it difficult to deliver these services. Social workers were forced to adapt to remote service delivery methods and began providing counseling, psychological support, and social assistance services through online platforms.¹⁰⁻¹¹ The roles of social workers during the crisis have been of vital importance, particularly for the homeless, the elderly, people with disabilities, and economically disadvantaged groups.¹²

One of the most significant impacts of the pandemic on the social work field has been the challenges faced from the perspectives of social justice and human rights.¹³⁻¹⁴ During the pandemic,

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barriers to accessing healthcare for low-income groups, an increase in domestic violence, and a rising need for mental health services have required social workers to develop new strategies.¹⁵⁻¹⁶ For example, a study conducted in the Netherlands demonstrates that the digital support services developed by social workers in response to the pandemic offer different advantages and disadvantages compared to traditional in-person services.¹¹ Additionally, during the pandemic, social workers have taken on a greater role in the field of mental health. The rise in cases of anxiety, depression, and stress during the pandemic has made social workers' efforts to support community mental health even more critical.¹⁰ Research conducted in Canada and Australia indicates that social workers play significant roles in protecting and supporting individuals' mental health during crisis situations.¹² The professional practices of social workers during the pandemic have given rise to new discussions regarding ethical and professional boundaries. For example, issues such as what social service policies should be implemented for individuals without access to healthcare, how methods for providing remote support to victims of domestic violence can be developed, and how social workers can protect themselves while working in the field have necessitated new regulations in professional practice.⁵ Additionally, the economic crisis triggered by the pandemic has necessitated the development of new approaches regarding how social workers can be more effective in combating poverty.⁹ The long-term effects of the pandemic on the social work profession are still being researched. Digital service delivery methods, new strategies for crisis intervention, and reforms in social work education raise questions about what can be done to make the social work profession more resilient and flexible in the future.¹⁷ The role and importance of social work education during times of crisis have increasingly become the subject of research. In particular, the effectiveness of social work professionals in crisis management during the COVID-19 pandemic has sparked significant debates regarding the adequacy of education in this field.⁸ Social work education focused on crisis periods should aim to equip students with practical skills, going beyond merely providing theoretical knowledge. However, studies in the existing literature on the adequacy of social work education during crisis periods have generally focused on Western countries, and it has been observed that social work education in Turkey has not been addressed in this context.¹⁸ Various studies in the international literature examine the relationship between crisis periods and social

work education. For example, studies conducted in Canada and Australia have analyzed the impact of the pandemic on social work students, revealing how educational models have evolved during times of crisis.^{10,12} These studies have emphasized the effects of online education models in particular and how the lack of field experience affects social work students' professional competence. A study conducted in the Netherlands, meanwhile, focused on the question of how effective social work education is in the context of crisis management and noted the need for a more practice-oriented curriculum to ensure students acquire the necessary skills during crises.¹¹ Similarly, a study conducted in Nigeria revealed that social work professionals' inability to fully grasp their roles in crisis response during the pandemic stemmed from deficiencies in educational programs.⁹ Social work education in Turkey lacks a comprehensive approach to crisis periods. The social work curriculum in Turkey is primarily based on traditional social work models and does not include comprehensive educational modules on crisis management, disaster response, and pandemics.¹⁸

Numerous studies have been conducted in the field of social work regarding the effects of the crisis period defined as the pandemic. In our country, it is observed that studies conducted by social workers and those related to the pandemic have primarily focused on the importance of social work and social workers during the outbreak.²⁵⁻²⁶ A review of the literature revealed that there is a lack of sufficient studies examining the education received by social work professionals in Turkey in relation to their professional experiences during the pandemic. In this regard, this study is considered highly significant in terms of the contribution it will make to the literature.

The aim of this study is to examine the professional experiences of social workers in Turkey during the pandemic from the perspective of social work education and to assess the adequacy of the curriculum in the context of crisis management. Additionally, this study aims to contribute to the literature by analyzing the professional transformations experienced by social workers during the pandemic and the implications of these experiences for the educational process. Consequently, recommendations will be presented to better equip social work education to address future crises.

In this context, the research questions have been formulated as follows:

1. What changes have occurred in the professional practices of social workers during the pandemic?
2. What challenges did social workers face during the

pandemic, and how did they respond to these challenges?

3. How should social work education be structured to prepare for similar future crises?

pandemic, barriers to accessing healthcare for low-income groups, an increase in domestic violence, and a rising need for mental health services have required social workers to develop new strategies.¹⁵⁻¹⁶ For example, a study conducted in the Netherlands demonstrates that the digital support services developed by social workers in response to the pandemic offer different advantages and disadvantages compared to traditional in-person services.¹¹ Additionally, during the pandemic, social workers have taken on a greater role in the field of mental health. The rise in cases of anxiety, depression, and stress during the pandemic has made social workers' efforts to support community mental health even more critical.¹⁰ Research conducted in Canada and Australia indicates that social workers play significant roles in protecting and supporting individuals' mental health during crisis situations.¹²

The professional practices of social workers during the pandemic have given rise to new discussions regarding ethical and professional boundaries. For example, issues such as what social service policies should be implemented for individuals without access to healthcare, how methods for providing remote support to victims of domestic violence can be developed, and how social workers can protect themselves while working in the field have necessitated new regulations in professional practice.⁵ Additionally, the economic crisis triggered by the pandemic has necessitated the development of new approaches regarding how social workers can be more effective in combating poverty.⁹ The long-term effects of the pandemic on the social work profession are still being researched. Digital service delivery methods, new strategies for crisis intervention, and reforms in social work education raise questions about what can be done to make the social work profession more resilient and flexible in the future.¹⁷

The role and importance of social work education during times of crisis have increasingly become the subject of research. In particular, the effectiveness of social work professionals in crisis management during the COVID-19 pandemic has sparked significant debates regarding the adequacy of education in this field.⁸ Social work education focused on crisis periods should aim to equip students with practical skills, going beyond merely providing theoretical knowledge.

However, studies in the existing literature on the adequacy of social work education during crisis periods have generally focused on Western countries, and it has been observed that social work education in Turkey has not been addressed in this context.¹⁸ Various studies in the international literature examine the relationship between crisis periods and social work education. For example, studies conducted in Canada and Australia have analyzed the impact of the pandemic on social work students, revealing how educational models have evolved during times of crisis.^{10,12} These studies have emphasized the effects of online education models in particular and how the lack of field experience affects social work students' professional competence. A study conducted in the Netherlands, meanwhile, focused on the question of how effective social work education is in the context of crisis management and noted the need for a more practice-oriented curriculum to ensure students acquire the necessary skills during crises.¹¹ Similarly, a study conducted in Nigeria revealed that social work professionals' inability to fully grasp their roles in crisis response during the pandemic stemmed from deficiencies in educational programs.⁹ Social work education in Turkey lacks a comprehensive approach to crisis periods. The social work curriculum in Turkey is primarily based on traditional social work models and does not include comprehensive educational modules on crisis management, disaster response, and pandemics.¹⁸

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In this context, the research questions have been formulated as follows:

1. What changes have occurred in the professional practices of social workers during the pandemic?
2. What challenges did social workers face during the pandemic, and how did they respond to these challenges?
3. How should social work education be structured to prepare for similar future crises?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Model

This study is a qualitative research project using a phenomenological design aimed at gaining an in-depth understanding of social workers' professional experiences during the pandemic. Qualitative research allows for the examination of individuals' lived experiences and the challenges they face from their own perspectives, thereby making participants' voices more visible.¹⁹ Because qualitative research aims to make sense of events and experiences within their own contexts, it is considered a powerful tool for evaluating social workers' experiences during the pandemic.²⁰ Phenomenology, meanwhile, is an approach that examines individuals' experiences of a specific phenomenon and the meanings they ascribe to those experiences.²¹ The phenomenological approach focuses on how individuals make sense of the situations they directly experience, thereby enabling the identification of common themes.²² According to Ersoy, phenomenology investigates the ways in which individuals make sense of their experiences and suggests that even people who have lived through the same event may have different perspectives.²³ In this context, the study aims to analyze the diverse experiences, professional practices, and challenges faced by social workers in the field during the pandemic, and to evaluate these within the framework of the social work education they have received.

Study Group

In this study, the study group was determined using the criterion sampling technique, one of the purposeful sampling methods. Purposeful sampling is a method based on the researcher selecting individuals who are knowledgeable about

the subject in order to obtain the most efficient data with limited resources.²⁴ Accordingly, two main criteria were used to determine the participants in the study:

1. Graduation from schools offering social work education at the undergraduate level with a similar curriculum,
2. Actively engaging in professional work during the pandemic.

In this context, a total of 12 social workers—6 graduates of Istanbul University-Cerrahpaşa and 6 graduates of Istanbul Medipol University—were included in the study. It is stated that the ideal sample size for phenomenological studies is around 10 participants.²² Accordingly, the study achieved the recommended ideal number of participants.

The reason for including individuals who graduated from social work programs with curricula similar to that of the study group was to assess the impact of the educational process on professional practice. By examining whether there were differences in the field practices of professionals with the same academic background, the study sought to understand the impact of social work education on professional competencies during the pandemic. Additionally, the fact that participants work in various social work practice areas (Local Governments, Ministry of Family and Social Services, Ministry of Justice, etc.) has broadened the scope of the research, allowing for the comparison of diverse professional experiences. The primary rationale for forming the study group from social work professionals actively engaged in their roles during the pandemic was that these individuals possess direct experience with the pandemic and are in a position to reliably assess its impact on professional practice.

The sociodemographic information of the participants in the study group is presented in Table 1. While the participants' names were coded as P-1, P-2, P-3... P-12, while the universities from which the participants graduated were coded as IUC (Istanbul University Cerrahpaşa) and IMÜ (Istanbul Medipol University). At the end of each participant's comments, the participant's code, length of experience, and the code of the university from which they graduated were included (Participant 1, 3.5 years, IUC).

Data Collection Tool

A semi-structured interview form was used as the data collection tool in this study. Semi-structured interviews allow the researcher flexibility while enabling the collection of systematic and in-depth responses to the defined research questions.²² The interview form used in the study consists of

two main sections. The first section includes sociodemographic information such as participants' gender, age, education level, field of work, and length of professional experience, while the second section contains research-specific questions focusing on social workers' professional experiences during the pandemic, changes in their work routines, the role of the social work profession and discipline during the pandemic, and the adequacy of social work education in crisis situations.

To enhance the reliability of the data collected from participants as part of the study, the interview form was developed based on a literature review, evaluated by two academics specializing in the field and a social worker, and finalized after necessary revisions were made following a pilot study.

Data Collection Process

Prior to beginning data collection for this study, ethical approval was obtained from the Istanbul Medipol University Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee, as per Decision No. 86 dated August 3, 2021. Data were collected between September 16, 2021, and October 24, 2021. The interview method was used to collect data for the study, and interviews were conducted with six social workers who graduated from the Department of Social Work at Istanbul Medipol University and six social workers who graduated from the Department of Social Work at Istanbul University-Cerrahpaşa. Due to pandemic conditions, all interviews were conducted online via the Zoom platform, and each session lasted an average of 40 minutes.

Before the interviews began, participants were provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, scope, and procedures; the principle of informed consent was applied in accordance with the study's ethical framework. All interviews were audio- and video-recorded with the participants' consent. Additionally, to ensure participants felt comfortable, a brief conversation on everyday topics was held before moving on to the semi-structured interview format, thereby creating a safe communication environment. It was clearly stated to participants that no personal information would be requested and that the shared data would be anonymized and used solely for scientific purposes. During the interviews, an interactive and supportive communication style was adopted, and care was taken to build trust in a way that encouraged participants' active engagement in the process.

Data Analysis

In this study, descriptive analysis—one of the qualitative data analysis methods—was employed, and the data obtained were systematically coded using the NVIVO 12 software and classified under specific themes. Descriptive analysis ensures that participants' statements are systematically organized, supported by direct quotations, and interpreted in line with the identified themes.²² The data obtained from the interviews were transferred to the NVIVO 12 software, and the processes of data management, coding, and thematic analysis were first carried out. In the initial phase, the raw data was transcribed, uploaded to NVIVO 12, and analyzed using open coding. The coding process was conducted based on predefined concepts aligned with the research questions; however, new concepts that emerged in the participants' narratives were also incorporated into the coding system.

The analysis process consisted of four main stages:

1. Data Organization and Coding: Data obtained from audio and video recordings was first transcribed word for word, then organized in NVIVO 12 software using codes based on themes.
2. Theme Generation: The coded data was categorized based on similarities and differences, and main themes were developed from these categories. The themes were defined to reflect social workers' professional experiences during the pandemic and the adequacy of social work education in the context of crisis management.
3. Supporting Findings with Direct Quotes: Direct quotes were included to present participants' statements more effectively, thereby enhancing the reliability and transparency of the findings.
4. Interpretation of Data and Drawing Conclusions: The analyzed data were interpreted in light of the existing literature and evaluated in terms of the effectiveness of social work education during the pandemic.

As part of the descriptive analysis process, a second coding was conducted by an independent researcher to enhance the reliability of the study, and coding consistency was reviewed. Additionally, expert opinions were sought to ensure the validity of the themes, and measures were taken to ensure the internal validity of the study.

Table 1. Sociodemographic Characteristics of Participants

Participants	Gender	Years of Experience	Employer	Year of Graduation
Participant 1	Male	3.5 Years	Social Services Center	2017
Participant 2	Male	1 Year	Municipality	2017
Participant 3	Female	2,5 Years	Municipality	2017
Participant 4	Female	1,5 Years	Municipality	2017
Participant 5	Female	6 Years	Social Services Center	2015
Participant 6	Male	6 Years	Social Services Center	2015
Participant 7	Female	1 Year	Municipality	2019
Participant 8	Female	1 Year	Nonprofit Organization	2019
Participant 9	Male	1 Year	Municipality	2019
Participant 10	Female	2 Years	Municipality	2019
Participant 11	Male	2 Years	Nonprofit Organization	2019
Participant 12	Female	1 Year	Municipality	2019

RESULTS

The findings regarding the themes and subthemes identified through the data analysis conducted as part of the study are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Themes and Subthemes

1. Social Work Practices During Pandemics and Crises	An Overview of Social Work Interventions in the Field
	The Roles of Social Workers During a Crisis
2. Shortcomings in Crisis and Disaster Response Training in Social Work Education	Inadequate Training in Crisis Management and Disaster Response
	The Gap Between Theoretical Knowledge and Practical Application
	Lack of Psychosocial Support and Psychological First Aid Training
3. Challenges Faced by Social Workers During the Pandemic and the Impact of Training	Shortcomings in Rapid Decision-Making and Response Processes
	Inadequacy of Support Mechanisms Erosion of Professional Identity
4. Recommendations for Crisis Intervention and Disaster Management in Social Work Education	Incorporating Crisis Intervention and Disaster Management Courses into the Curriculum
	Strengthening Practical Training and Internship Programs
	Providing Supervision and Support Mechanisms for Social Workers

1. Social Work Practices During Pandemics and Crises

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought about fundamental changes in the way social workers operate and has revealed important insights into how social work interventions take shape during crises. This section examines social work interventions in the field, the challenges faced by practitioners, and findings related to crisis management processes.

1.1. Perspectives on Social Work Interventions in the Field

During the pandemic, social work interventions focused largely on social assistance, marking a period in which field workers moved away from their traditional roles and took on distribution tasks. While social workers carried out interventions for those in need, they were also forced to adapt to the new working conditions created by the pandemic.

Participant 2 described encountering tasks that were inconsistent with the essence of social work while working in the field during the pandemic, stating:

"We went to people's homes for social assessments during this period. Our interactions with the applicants changed significantly—'Can you wear a mask? Is anyone in the household sick with COVID?' So there was always a sense of keeping our distance. Aside from that, we also did tasks unrelated to our regular work—like distributing boxes and tablets... since we were working for the municipality, we handled some of these kinds of tasks as well." (Participant 2, 1 Year, IUC)

Similarly, Participant 9, who noted that social workers drifted away from their professional practices during the pandemic, emphasizes that at some point, social workers were reduced to mere aid distribution personnel:

"Professor, of course, sometimes they assigned us distribution tasks as well. For example, we had to distribute cards to the families whose cases were approved after our review. And with these cards, things are piling up quickly—the process is moving fast. The team says we need to put the reviews on hold for this one-week period because the cards need to be distributed urgently. There was a tablet project—because of the pandemic, children were cut off from education, so we urgently needed to distribute forty thousand tablets. At times, we'd pull some teams into tablet distribution, and so on. So,

during the pandemic, I'd say we essentially became distribution staff in a way that had nothing to do with social services." (Participant 9, 1 Year, IMU)

The findings reveal that social workers were diverted from their primary roles during the pandemic and directed toward aid distribution, and highlight how the social work profession has transformed in the context of crisis management.

1.2. The Roles of Social Workers During the Crisis

During the pandemic, social workers assumed critical roles in crisis management but encountered significant structural and organizational shortcomings throughout this process. In particular, uncertainties arose during rapid decision-making processes, and field operations were frequently carried out based on sudden interventions and directives. Furthermore, the lack of adequate resources among social workers in situations requiring crisis management has limited the effectiveness of professional interventions.

Participant 1 describes how the need for rapid decision-making during the crisis combined with on-the-ground challenges, and how operations often proceeded in an unplanned manner, as follows:

"The Ministry only wanted us to conduct inspections or investigations in emergency situations. But that's really a difficult situation—I mean, what exactly do you mean by an 'emergency'? It doesn't necessarily have to be an urgent case; sometimes we just need to go there, or we need to get a signature from a citizen, collect documents, or take a look. So, for that reason, it felt like it wasn't managed well." (Participant 1, 3.5 years, Istanbul University College)

Similarly, Participant 9 notes that social workers struggled in the field during the pandemic because they were not adequately prepared for crisis management:

"We faced an extra challenge when transitioning from social work in our student lives to social work in our professional lives, especially since this process coincided with the pandemic. Because while a social worker should indeed have planned intervention stages, I also realized that, above all, a social worker must be able to make decisions very quickly." (Participant 9, 1 Year, IMU)

These statements indicate that social workers experienced a lack of guidance in crisis management and intervention processes during the pandemic, and that this situation had significant impacts on their professional practices. The conflict between the necessity of rapid decision-making and the planned intervention approach in social work created serious professional tension for field workers.

2. Shortcomings in Social Work Education Regarding Crisis and Disaster Response

The pandemic has exposed the shortcomings of social work education regarding crisis and disaster response. It has been observed that educational programs are largely structured within a theoretical framework and do not provide sufficient training for real-world crisis scenarios. In particular, deficiencies in crisis management, psychosocial support processes, and practical training have exacerbated the challenges faced by social workers during the pandemic.

2.1. Inadequate Training in Crisis Management and Disaster Response

The lack of sufficient training in crisis and disaster response within social work undergraduate programs has led to serious shortcomings in social workers' ability to develop crisis management skills during the pandemic. The absence of a structured training process on how to respond during crises has forced professionals to learn through on-the-job experience. Participant 8 expressed the lack of training in disaster management and crisis response as follows:

"We didn't receive any training on disasters. How could we have managed this process? In this regard, we were all like fish out of water." (Participant 8, 1 Year, IMU)

Similarly, Participant 1 states that they did not receive training specific to the pandemic and that theoretical knowledge regarding crisis intervention is insufficient, as follows:

"I don't recall receiving any training specifically about the pandemic—about what we should do when faced with it. But here's the thing: social work already requires us to develop situation-specific solutions when encountering different circumstances. Even if pandemic-specific training wasn't provided, I believe the general purpose of the training was exactly that." (Participant 1, 3.5 years, IUC)

These statements highlight the inadequacy of theoretical and practical content related to crisis management in social work education. It is clear that a comprehensive training process is

needed to be able to intervene during crises such as a pandemic.

2.2. The Gap Between Theoretical Knowledge and Practical Application

It is often noted that social work education is largely shaped by a theoretical framework, while practical applications remain insufficient. The fact that the experiences gained in the field are not adequately reflected in university education has led graduates to feel uncertain about what to do in crisis situations.

Participant 12 highlights the disconnect between theoretical education and field practice with the following words:

"We were forced to present social work in the field as merely a profession that provides economic support because, due to the need for quick decision-making, we could only offer referrals. Our theoretical knowledge was insufficient to enable effective intervention in the field." (Participant 12, 1 Year, IMU)

Similarly, Participant 6 states that there was no comprehensive practical training on crisis processes at the university:

"We took a course on crisis intervention, but we didn't actually cover what to do or what needs to be done during a pandemic. Why? One of our professors had said, 'The word "pandemic" has only recently entered our vocabulary and our lives.' Of course, at that time, such a course didn't exist at Hacettepe University, let alone Istanbul University. Universities should provide comprehensive training on crisis management and the appropriate course of action for social work professionals during disaster situations." (Participant 6, 6 Years, IUC)

These findings reveal that social work education is disconnected from field realities and fails to adequately equip students with the practical skills needed for rapid and effective intervention during crises.

2.3. Lack of Training in Psychosocial Support and Psychological First Aid

One of the greatest shortcomings during the pandemic was that social workers were not sufficiently equipped in the areas of psychosocial support and psychological first aid. It was observed that while providing psychological support and applying psychosocial intervention methods are of great importance, particularly during times of crisis, these topics

were not adequately addressed in the training process.

Participant 7 expressed the shortcomings they experienced regarding psychological support and stress management as follows:

"I don't think I received sufficient training in psychology during my education. Perhaps I should have developed myself a bit more in this area. We had a few courses like 'Introduction to Psychology,' but since families were so emotionally drained, we fell short in providing psychological support." (Participant 7, 1 Year, IMU)

Similarly, Participant 5 highlights the lack of psychological first aid training in the field:

"Why did we only learn about psychological first aid once we were out in the field? Why were we trained solely on laws and regulations? Why didn't we have a class on drawing analysis? Why didn't we take psychodrama? Why didn't we see anything about play therapy with children? The social work curriculum must be strengthened with practical training focused on crises." (Participant 5, 6 Years, IUC)

These statements clearly demonstrate that social work education is lacking in the areas of psychological support, trauma-sensitive intervention during crises, and psychosocial support services. In particular, ensuring that social work professionals receive psychological first aid training during disaster and crisis periods will enable them to be more effective in their fieldwork.

3. Challenges Faced by Social Workers During the Pandemic and the Impact of Education

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly affected the roles and professional practices of social workers in the field, creating many new challenges and uncertainties. Rapid decision-making during crises, insufficient support mechanisms, and a weakened sense of professional identity were among the key challenges social workers faced during the pandemic. These challenges, combined with gaps in social work education, led to greater difficulties for professionals during crisis situations.

3.1. Shortcomings in Rapid Decision-Making and Intervention Processes

Social workers typically focus their work on planned intervention processes. However, the necessity of making

rapid and immediate decisions during the pandemic posed a significant challenge for professionals who lacked adequate training in this area. The absence of a clear roadmap on how to act during crises has forced social workers in the field to develop their own solutions.

Participant 1 describes how challenging field operations were from a crisis management perspective during the pandemic:

"The Ministry only wanted us to conduct inspections/investigations during emergencies. But this is really a difficult situation—what exactly do you mean by an emergency? It doesn't necessarily have to be an urgent case; sometimes we have to go there, or we need to get a signature from the citizen, collect documents, or make an inspection. That's why it felt like it wasn't managed well. We didn't have a clear roadmap for what to do during crises." (Participant 1, 3.5 years, IUC)

Similarly, Participant 10 notes that keeping up with the increased demands during the pandemic and making quick decisions was quite challenging:

"The volume of requests increased significantly; keeping up with them, making quick decisions, providing urgent interventions, and meeting expectations made managing this process quite difficult." (Participant 10, 2 Years, IMU)

These statements indicate that social workers, who are accustomed to planned interventions during crises, struggled with sudden and rapid decision-making processes. The lack of crisis intervention training tailored to extraordinary situations like the pandemic has led field workers to feel inadequate during intervention processes.

3.2. Inadequacy of Support Mechanisms

During the pandemic, the lack of guidance and supervision mechanisms to support social workers in their fieldwork has become a major problem for professionals working on the front lines. Social workers have been left to fend for themselves, both in terms of professional decision-making processes and in terms of experiencing psychological burnout.

Participant 11 expressed that social workers were deprived of adequate guidance and support mechanisms during crisis situations in the pandemic, stating:

"We did not receive any supportive training while working in the field; no guidance was provided on how to intervene in crisis situations.

There was no supervisory support either, so we tried to manage the situation entirely on our own." (Participant 11, 2 Years, IMU)

Similarly, Participant 5 notes that professional organizations and institutions did not provide sufficient support to social workers during the pandemic:

"Social workers were left very much on their own during the pandemic. Professional organizations, supervision systems, and psychosocial support mechanisms did not function. Many of my colleagues experienced burnout because we didn't know what to expect and there was no one to turn to for support." (Participant 5, 6 Years, IUC)

These findings indicate that one of the most critical areas requiring support for social workers during the pandemic is professional supervision and guidance services. To enable effective intervention during crises, social workers must not be left alone, and support mechanisms for their fieldwork must be developed.

3.3. Erosion of Professional Identity

During the pandemic, social workers were sidelined from their core duties and viewed solely as aid distribution personnel, leading to a serious erosion of the profession's identity. While social workers should be seen as integral to psychosocial support and social intervention processes during crises, they were confined to administrative tasks within aid organizations.

Participant 12 expressed that during the pandemic, social workers were seen more as aid distribution personnel than as providers of psychosocial support, stating:

"Social workers were seen more as aid distribution personnel than as providers of psychosocial support in the field. During the pandemic, we were forced to put our profession's primary function—psychosocial support—on the back burner." (Participant 12, 1 Year, IMU)

Similarly, Participant 9 states that during the pandemic, social workers were directed entirely toward logistical tasks, with their core responsibilities being overlooked, as follows:

"During the pandemic, the tasks assigned to us were about distributing aid rather than practicing social work. We distributed cards and tablets, meaning we stepped outside the scope of our profession." (Participant 9, 1 Year, IMU)

These statements indicate that the social work profession was limited to social assistance activities during the pandemic, thereby narrowing professional roles. However, the core duties of social workers include providing psychosocial support during crises, developing community-based interventions, and conducting empowerment initiatives for disadvantaged groups. This loss of professional role during the pandemic has weakened social workers' perception of their professional identity and led to the field's true potential being overlooked.

4. Recommendations for Crisis Intervention and Disaster Management in Social Work Education

The pandemic has clearly highlighted gaps in crisis management and disaster response within social work education. To ensure that social work professionals can play an effective and well-equipped role during crisis situations, it is necessary to revise educational curricula, increase practical training, and strengthen in-service support mechanisms. In this context, recommendations that can be developed for crisis intervention in social work education are discussed below under three main headings.

4.1. Inclusion of Crisis Intervention and Disaster Management Courses in the Curriculum

Making courses on crisis management and disaster intervention mandatory in the social work curriculum will ensure that social workers are better prepared during times of crisis. The systematic development of knowledge and skills related to crisis processes will enable social workers to carry out effective interventions during disasters and emergencies. Participant 6 expresses the lack of comprehensive training on crisis processes and the need to make such courses mandatory as follows:

"The pandemic has now become a part of our lives. Covid ends, another crisis begins. Universities need to offer comprehensive courses on how social work professionals should proceed during crisis management and disaster processes. It is essential that such a program be implemented and taught as a mandatory course in universities." (Participant 6, 6 Years, IUC)

Similarly, Participant 9 highlights the lack of crisis management training and emphasizes the need to add specialized courses to the curriculum to ensure social work students are prepared for crisis processes:

"Social work students should be taught topics such as how to manage a crisis, what crisis

management entails, and under what circumstances a crisis occurs. We saw our shortcomings in this area very clearly during the pandemic." (Participant 9, 1 Year, IMU)

These statements highlight the need to incorporate comprehensive courses on crisis intervention, disaster management, and emergency planning into the social work curriculum. As a result, social work professionals will be better equipped to handle crisis situations and carry out effective interventions during crises.

4.2. Strengthening Practical Training and Internship Programs

Supporting theoretical knowledge with practical applications will enable social workers to assume more effective roles in crisis intervention processes. However, the current curriculum lacks sufficient practical training and field experience related to crises. Therefore, it is necessary to increase practical training, extend internship periods, and incorporate case studies based on crisis scenarios into the curriculum.

Participant 1 expresses the need for more practical work in social work education as follows:

"First of all, I think there needs to be more practical work. Of course, theoretical knowledge is important, but without practical experience, it's really difficult—especially in a challenging field like social work. When I first started, I thought, 'Where have I ended up?' because you encounter so many different situations and have to make decisions that affect people's lives." (Participant 1, 3.5 years, Istanbul University)

Similarly, Participant 12 highlights the lack of field practice in crisis management processes and the need to provide students with more practical experience:

"We should have the opportunity to practice using case studies and simulations in crisis management training. We need to gain experience before going out into the field." (Participant 12, 1st Year, IMU)

These statements indicate the need to increase field experience related to crises in social work education. Developing case simulations, applied internship programs, and multidisciplinary training models at universities will ensure that professionals are better prepared when they enter the field.

4.3. Providing Supervision and Support Mechanisms

for Social Workers

One of the biggest challenges faced by social workers during the pandemic was being left to fend for themselves in the field and lacking adequate supervision support. Therefore, it is essential to establish supervision programs for social workers operating during crises, increase in-service training, and strengthen psychosocial support mechanisms.

Participant 11 expresses the need to increase in-service training during crisis periods as follows:

“Social workers were left on their own during the pandemic. In-service training should be provided during crisis periods to ensure that social workers are better equipped.” (Participant 11, 2 Years, IMU)

Similarly, Participant 10 states that the lack of supervision support had a negative impact on fieldwork practices, as follows:

“We needed psychological support. We worked constantly in the field and experienced burnout, but there was no support mechanism in place for us.” (Participant 10, 2 years, IMU)

These findings highlight the need for social workers not to be left alone during crisis situations and underscore the importance of developing in-service supervision mechanisms. To prevent social workers from experiencing burnout and to enable them to provide more effective interventions, in-service training, guidance systems, and psychosocial support mechanisms must be strengthened.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to evaluate the adequacy of the social work curriculum in the context of crisis management by examining the professional experiences of social workers in Turkey during the pandemic period from the perspective of social work education. Accordingly, the research analyzed the professional transformations experienced by practitioners during the pandemic and the reflections of these experiences on the educational process within four core themes: social work practice during pandemic and crisis periods, existing deficiencies in crisis and disaster response within social work education, the challenges encountered by practitioners during the pandemic and the impact of education on these challenges, and recommendations for the improvement of social work education. These interrelated themes and the findings obtained provide a foundation for presenting concrete proposals aimed

at equipping social work education with a more robust structure in preparation for future crises.

The first notable finding of the study is that social work practice during the pandemic shifted away from psychosocial support and empowerment-oriented interventions, becoming reduced to the distribution of social assistance and logistical and administrative processes. Kaya et al., in their study conducted specifically in Turkey, associate this transformation with the foregrounding of monetary needs under the pressure of the economic crisis²⁵. However, this process of instrumentalization extends beyond a matter of mere practical adaptation. Banks et al. emphasize that this situation carries the risk of the profession drifting away from its emancipatory nature toward a controlling structure, with service users being pushed into a passive position⁵. While an expansion of professional roles would be anticipated during periods of crisis, the blurring of professional boundaries and the reduction of practice to logistical activities instead constitute a significant area of debate with regard to the professional identity and autonomy of the discipline.

Underlying this process of instrumentalization is a structural unpreparedness for crisis management. Although participants reported having personally experienced the critical importance of rapid and flexible decision-making in sudden crisis situations, they indicated that their educational processes had not equipped them adequately for such scenarios. Onalu et al. corroborate this finding by determining that the predominantly theoretical, rather than practice-oriented, structure of existing curricula renders them ineffective in preparing practitioners for chaotic processes such as the pandemic⁹. Afrouz further notes that frontline practitioners faced considerable uncertainty and difficulty due to their lack of training specific to disaster management and public health crises¹⁷. This state of unpreparedness in the field compelled practitioners to devise improvisational solutions grounded in intuition, skill, and resilience beyond bureaucratic procedures, while simultaneously generating the risk of being overwhelmed by what may be termed "ethical logistics" burdens, such as the allocation of limited resources.

Another structural problem intertwined with unpreparedness for crisis management is the profound disconnect between theoretical knowledge and field practice. Participants particularly emphasized that the theoretical knowledge acquired during undergraduate education proved insufficient under the chaotic conditions of the pandemic period. The

predominant focus of educational programs on micro-level case studies, coupled with inadequate exposure to real-life scenarios, is identified as the primary source of graduates feeling vulnerable in the face of macro-level crises. In this regard, Dominelli advocates for a reconceptualization of social work education from a crisis preparedness perspective, proposing the integration of specific courses such as disaster management and public health into the curriculum, as well as a restructuring toward an action-oriented framework centered on risk management competencies — framing these as both academic and professional imperatives⁷. Afrouz similarly draws attention to the utility of experiential learning methods, such as scenario-building exercises supported by digital technologies, role-playing, and crisis simulations, in bridging this gap.¹⁷

Deficiencies in the provision of psychosocial support constitute the dimension of the theoretical-practical disconnect as reflected in the field of mental health. Despite the fact that supporting mental health during crisis periods represents one of the core responsibilities of social work, participants reported not feeling adequately equipped in this domain. The predominantly micro-intervention-oriented structure of existing education lays the groundwork for practitioners to experience a sense of being overwhelmed when confronted with macro-level social problems such as the pandemic.^{9,13} The more robust positioning of psychological first aid and trauma-informed content within the curriculum appears indispensable for addressing this critical gap.

Finally, the absence of supervision and institutional guidance emerges as a significant factor that exacerbates all of the aforementioned difficulties. Global research confirms that practitioners who are unable to receive emotional support or professional guidance from their supervisors feel unsupported in stressful environments.⁵ In the Turkish context, this situation, compounded by the loss of motivation arising from increased workloads and extended shifts, markedly elevates the risk of occupational trauma and burnout²⁵. Numerous studies conducted in Turkey across different periods similarly draw attention to the necessity of supervision.²⁷⁻²⁸ When all of these findings are considered collectively, the integration of crisis intervention and disaster management courses into the curriculum, the strengthening of practice-based training, and the implementation of supervision mechanisms grounded in compassionate leadership emerge as the foremost transformation agendas for social work education.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to evaluate the adequacy of the existing educational system in the context of crisis management by examining the professional experiences of social workers in Turkey during the COVID-19 pandemic from the perspective of social work education. The findings reveal that the pandemic process gave rise to significant transformations in social work practice, and that these transformations are largely associated with deficiencies in the educational process.

According to the research findings, the professional roles of social workers underwent considerable change during the pandemic, with psychosocial support and empowerment-based practices largely being displaced by social assistance distribution and logistical activities. This situation resulted in the fundamental functions of the social work profession being relegated to the background and a weakening of professional identity perception. Furthermore, the necessity for rapid decision-making and effective intervention during crisis processes demonstrated that the existing educational system does not provide adequate preparation for such circumstances.

The findings clearly demonstrate that social work education remains predominantly within a theoretical framework and that practice-oriented skills are inadequate. Significant deficiencies were identified particularly in the areas of crisis management, disaster response, psychosocial support, and psychological first aid. In addition, it was observed that social work practitioners lacked adequate supervision and institutional support mechanisms during the pandemic period, a circumstance that heightened the risk of professional burnout.

In light of these findings, the following recommendations have been developed:

- Courses focused on crisis management, disaster response, and emergency planning should be mandatorily incorporated into undergraduate social work programs. These courses must be supported not solely by theoretical content but also by practice-oriented components.
- In order to ensure students are adequately prepared for crisis situations, case analyses, simulations, role-playing techniques, and field-based practices should be expanded. Internship programs should be restructured to be of greater duration and enhanced quality.
- Social work students should receive comprehensive training in psychological first aid, trauma-informed

approaches, and mental health interventions during crisis periods.

- Regular supervision mechanisms should be established for social work practitioners, and psychosocial support and guidance services should be provided during crisis periods.
- Training pertaining to online service delivery methods, which gained considerable prominence during the pandemic process, should be integrated into the curriculum, and digital social work practices should be further developed.
- In order to prevent social work practitioners from being confined solely to assistance distribution during crisis periods, the ethical principles and professional boundaries of the profession should be safeguarded and reinforced at the institutional level.

In conclusion, the pandemic process has unequivocally demonstrated the necessity of reconceptualizing social work education from the standpoint of crisis preparedness. Equipping social work education with a flexible, practice-oriented, and crisis-sensitive structure is of paramount importance in order to enable more effective and comprehensive interventions when confronted with similar crises in the future.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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No

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